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revitalizing Democracy in Europe.*

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D5.1 Feminist Activists online course

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#	Participant	Participant organisation name	Short Name	Country
1	COO	VILABS OE	VIL	EL
2	BEN	AALBORG UNIVERSITET	AAU	DK
3	BEN	SCUOLA NORMALE SUPERIORE	SNS	IT
4	BEN	UNIVERSIDAD COMPLUTENSE DE MADRID	UCM	ES
5	BEN	SMART VENICE SRL	SV	IT
6	BEN	ALTERNATIVES EUROPEENNES ASSOCIATION	EA	FR
7	BEN	UNIWERSYTET GDANSKI	UG	PL
8	BEN	ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	AUTH	EL
9	BEN	MIROVNI INSTITUT	MI	SI
10	BEN	KOC UNIVERSITY	KU	TR
11	BEN	UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI	UL	SI

CONTENTS

1.	Introduction	4
1.1.	The FIERCE Project – Summary	4
1.2.	Description of WP5	4
1.3.	The FIERCE course: methodology and background information	4
2.	Course description	6
2.1.	Learning objectives	6
3.	Structure of the course	8
3.1.	List of lessons	8
3.1.1.	Module 1: Anti-gender mobilizations in the current political context and feminist responses	8
3.1.2.	Module 2: Intersectional feminist mobilizations	8
3.1.3.	Module 3: Global Challenges, Feminisms and Democracy	9
3.2.	Materials	10
3.3.	Final quiz	10
4.	List of course lecturers	13
5.	References	17

List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

ABM	Advisory Board Member
D	Deliverable
NGO	Non-governmental organisations
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

1.1. The FIERCE Project – Summary

FIERCE aims to provide sound theoretical and practical knowledge and tools to revitalize alliances between the feminist movement, civil society and political decision makers in a context of growing social inequalities, political disaffection and strengthening of populist radical right anti-gender actors and discourses. The research uses an interdisciplinary, multi-dimensional and multi-level framework, that aims to overcome the limitations of both disciplinary scholarships and nationalist methodologies. FIERCE develops in-depth understanding of feminist and anti-feminist/anti-gender movements, activities and discourses, and their impact on the institutional arena and on policy outcomes, focusing on the period 2010-2021. These actors, and especially the feminist movement, will be studied through frame analysis, political ethnography and Social Network Analysis on the background of key gender debates and controversies prefigured to be situated in the areas of: labour market; health and reproductive rights; LGBTQ+ rights; migration; and gender-based violence. FIERCE will cover eight case studies (France, Italy, Greece, Slovenia, Turkey, Denmark, Poland, Spain) representing a wide variety of country contexts in socio-political, geographical and welfare terms. FIERCE moves beyond a country-based approach and provides a cross-cutting comparative analysis of the way debates and controversies on gender have influenced the dynamics and output of the policy process. Building on co-creation methods and on a strong alliance with civil society organisations, FIERCE proposes pilot actions that can reinvigorate democratic practices, in line with feminist inclusive visions for the future of democracy. FIERCE thereby sets out a bottom-up, problem-driven and impact-oriented approach, bridging academic knowledge, policy-making and bottom-up democratic strategies.

1.2. Description of WP5

Work Package 5 (WP5), “Innovative Strategies and Solution Pathways,” began in Month 10 (M10) of the project and consists of three main tasks. Task 5.1 involved the establishment of a transnational network of feminist activists and public actors, which convened five times over the course of the project—twice in person and three times online. Task 5.2, which this deliverable is part of, focused on the launch of a Feminist Activists Winter School and the development of an online e-learning course. Task 5.3 entailed the drafting of policy briefs and the creation of a policy toolkit, based on the outcomes of the co-creation processes carried out within the FIERCE project.

1.3. The FIERCE course: methodology and background information

The feminist activists’ online course “Learning Intersectional Feminism in Context: A Course on Strategies and Alliances in Times of Anti-Gender and Far-Right Movements” corresponds to D5.1 of the FIERCE project, consisting of an online self-paced course based on edited and subtitled videos from recordings of the winter school, which was organised in M27 as part of the [FIERCE Week](#) (T5.2), carried out in Venice from November 4th to 7th, 2024.

The FIERCE week was an event composed of different FIERCE initiatives, involving feminist activists, scholars, and FIERCE researchers and advisory board members. During the first day (November 4th, from 14:00 to 18:00), the third and last meeting of the transnational place took place (T4.3), focusing on the lessons learnt from the feminist action implemented as part of this lab, the “Five FIERCE Claims for a Feminist Europe” campaign, which targeted candidates to the European Parliament 2024 elections. The second and third days of the FIERCE week were dedicated to the FIERCE winter school (T5.2), whose sessions were recorded, becoming the main input of the online course. Finally, during the last day of FIERCE, the launch of the FIERCE feminist network took place (T5.1) as a space of transnational collaboration for feminist exchange and to build resistance to fight against the anti-gender backlash.

Within this framework, the FIERCE online course curriculum reflects the FIERCE winter school structure, with two additional lessons prepared by feminist activists, recorded after the event took place. The winter school was conceived as a mixed space of feminist knowledge creation, bridging research and activism/practice to advance intersectional feminist alliances and contrast the spread of anti-gender/anti-feminist discourses and politics.

The winter school aimed at not replicating traditional hierarchies in knowledge creation – where academic knowledge has a predominant role. One relevant element in the conception of the FIERCE winter school was the concept of critical friendship, where ‘critical friends’ are conceived as trusted individuals who pose thought-provoking questions, offer data to be examined from different perspectives, and provide constructive criticism in a friendly manner (Costa & Kallick, 1993). Chappell & Mackay (2021) reinterpret this concept in a feminist key as “researchers who may be aligned with the key tenets of the agenda being pursued by feminist actors [...] but they stand outside [...]” In the FITTER project, as detailed in D4.1 v.1, the concept is adapted to a context in which feminist social movements assume a critical perspective towards democratic institutions.

During the course, both researchers and activists shared the knowledge they were generating in a horizontal setting where different styles of knowledge sharing and presenting/performing were welcome. In particular, sessions included academic lectures by FIERCE researchers and the Advisory Board Members (ABM), presentations, and roundtable discussions from activists focused on their mobilisation practices. In addition, the FIERCE sister projects were also invited to participate in the winter school. After presentations, "feminist critical friendship" sessions and discussions were organised in plenary or smaller groups to give space to questions, criticism, and discussions on how the generated learnings can feed into feminist mobilisations and intersectional alliances.

The course structure was translated into the FIERCE curricula, organising three modules, which reflected the three thematic areas covered in the FIERCE week. More information about the modules, lessons, learning materials, and lecturers is provided in the following section.

2. Course description

The FIERCE Course is a self-paced programme reflecting the programme of the FIERCE Winter school, combining academic lectures by FIERCE researchers with presentations from activists. It invites participants to reflect on the current political scenario dominated by the far right, engage in discussions on future feminist strategies, and explore pathways for building intersectional alliances.

The course is organised into three modules, with a total of ten lessons. The first module focuses on anti-gender mobilisations in the current political context. The second module addresses intersectional feminist mobilisations in different country-level contexts. The third module examines transnational mobilisations, global challenges for the feminist movement, and democracy in Europe. Eight out of the ten lessons were recorded during the winter school and two additional sessions (lessons 4 and 7) were recorded between March and April 2025 with two activists who had participated of different activities of the FIERCE project. They were invited to speak of relevant themes for the course that had not been addressed during the winter school.

The course is available in Smart Venice's e-learning platform¹: <https://gender-research-docc.eu/courses/advancing-inclusive-gender-equality-plans-in-research-organizations/>. Participation is free of charge, requires [registration](#) and will be available for a minimum of two years after the end of the project in August 2025. The course is self-paced and untutored. A certificate can be obtained upon completion of the lessons and successful completion of the final quiz.

Target population of the course:

- Feminist activists
- Social movements activists interested in establishing intersectional alliances
- Non-governmental organisations (NGOs), think-tanks and charities
- Political actors and policymakers
- Academic and scholars, interested addressing the feminist and anti-gender movements
- Students (political and social sciences, gender studies, humanities)
- Gender experts, policy-makers, practitioners interested in the topics

Course dissemination

The course is being disseminated within the project networks, including the transnational network established as part of T5.1. In addition, academic partners are sharing the course with their students. Other dissemination efforts include the launch of a dedicated newsletter (to be released on July 2nd) and social media posts.

2.1. Learning objectives

Overall

- Analyse anti-gender and anti-feminist movements by examining their strategies, discourses, and impact on politics and society.
- Explore feminist mobilisations and intersectional alliances through case studies and activist insights.
- Examine transnational feminist activism and their responses to global challenges.
- Bridge research and activism to foster critical reflection, strengthen feminist alliances, and inspire strategic action.

¹ The dedicated page for the course inside the project's webpage is available at: <https://fierce-project.eu/fierce-course/>.

Module 1 Anti-gender mobilizations in the current political context and feminist responses

- Analyse the trends, discourses, and strategies used by anti-gender and anti-feminist actor
- Explore effective actions, forms of mobilisation, and techniques of resistance within the feminist movement.
- Examine real case studies from Turkey, France and Slovenia.

Module 2 Intersectional feminist mobilizations

- Discuss intersectional feminism and sophisticated racism.
- Gain first-hand insights into feminist mobilisations through the experiences of feminist activists, including:
 - The movement of care workers in Spain.
 - The actions of the European Roma Rights Centre to promote the inclusion of Roma women.
 - Activism for legal and safe abortion in Poland
 - equal access to medically assisted procreation in France

Module 3 Global Challenges, Feminisms and Democracy

- Explore the effects of multiple crises—socio-economic and climate—on gender politics and feminist activism.
- Analyse the new wave of feminist mobilisation, examining its key issues, organisational structures, alliances, outcomes, and repertoires of action.
- Look beyond the European Union with case studies on feminist mobilisations in Turkey and Georgia.

3. Structure of the course

The FIERCE course is organised in three modules with ten lessons and a final quiz. An online repository was built collectively with FIERCE partners and activists, providing materials for each. Following, details on the list of lessons, materials and the final quiz are provided.

3.1. List of lessons

Below, descriptions of the lessons included in the e-learning platform are provided:

3.1.1. Module 1: Anti-gender mobilizations in the current political context and feminist responses

Lesson 1: Project 2025 and Beyond: The global Spread of Anti-Gender and anti-feminist Actors and Frames

(Lise Rolandsen Augustin, Susi Meret – Aalborg University)

In this lesson's first half, professors from Aalborg university (AAU) Susi Meret and Lise Rolandsen Agustín, present the phenomena of intensifying anti-gender and anti-feminist mobilisation and the relevant organizations and transnational alliances, and provides a brief overview of the Project 2025 initiative. The second half of the lesson walks us through FIERCE preliminary research results concerning anti-gender and anti-feminist discourse and what frames and strategies are being used.

Lesson 2: Feminist movements resisting to anti-gender rise and backlash

(Deniz Bayram – Purple Roof Women's Shelter Foundation, Maëlle Noir – #NousToutes)

In this lesson, you can listen to a panel discussion between Deniz Bayram and Maëlle Noir, feminist activists from (Purple Roof Women's Shelter Foundation (Turkey) and NousToutes (France), who share concrete examples about feminist movements resisting anti-gender rise and backlash. Bayram presents the resistance practices of feminist movements in Turkey from a historical perspective, while Noir focuses on the strategies employed by the French movement #NousToutes.

Lesson 3: Resisting the Backlash: Anti-Gender Mobilizations in Europe and the Feminist Response

(Jasna Podreka – Univeristy of Ljubljana)

In this lesson, Jasna Podreka from the University of Ljubljana, shares preliminary findings on the actors, discourses and strategies characterizing the anti-gender movement, and the feminist responses and strategies (and their successes) used in response to anti-gender mobilization in the countries included in the FIERCE project.

Lesson 4: Feminist responses to the anti-gender backlash in Slovenia

(Sonja Lokar – Women's Lobby of Slovenia)

In this lesson, Sonja Lokar, President of the Women's Lobby of Slovenia, analyses the state of gender equality in Slovenia, offering a historical overview of backlash incidents and feminist responses. She also presents the contemporary anti-gender movement in Slovenia and shares the experience of parallel electoral campaigns as a strategy to push back.

3.1.2. Module 2: Intersectional feminist mobilizations

Lesson 5: White Innocence: Complexity and Challenges in Practicing Intersectional Feminism

(Victoria Showunmi – University College London)

In this lesson, professor from UCL Victoria Showunmi discusses intersectional feminism and sophisticated racism and shares the associated complexities and challenges in practicing it.

Lesson 6: Intersectional Feminist strategies - Panel discussion with feminist activists

(Anikó Orsós – European Roma Rights Centre, Rafaela Pimentel – Territorio Doméstico, Dominika Kasprowicz – Legal Abortion)

In this lesson, members from feminist organisations and movements share their strategies and results through an intersectional feminist perspective. First, Rafaela Pimentel, activist from the Spanish movement Territorio Doméstico discusses recent developments regarding the situation of domestic workers in Spain following the Spanish Government's ratification of Convention 189. This is followed by the presentation of Anikó Orsós, who shares how the ERRC approaches the intersection of Roma identity and gender in its activism and how it represents the rights of Roma women. Finally, Dominika Kasprowicz, Polish activist from Legal Abortion, describes how the context for abortion rights activism shifted following last year's political election results, and what strategies have Abortion Dream Team, Legal Abortion, and the Abortion Doulas Network employed to provide support.

Lesson 7: Advocacy for equal access to medically assisted procreation in France

(Veronique Cerasoli - SOS Homophobie)

In this lesson, Véronique Cerasoli, a French activist, provides practical recommendations of how to implement advocacy activities. She shares a real-life case from her organisation, SOS Homophobie, and their fight for the right to access medically assisted procreation in France.

3.1.3. Module 3: Global Challenges, Feminisms and Democracy

Lesson 8: Gender Politics and Feminist Activism in Times of Multiple Crises

(Birte Siim – Aalborg University)

In this lesson, Birte Siim, professor from Aalborg University, presents the effects of the multiple (socio-economic and climate) crisis for gender politics and feminist activism. She introduces Donna Haraway's approach to gender politics and provides an overview of ecological and environmental feminist frameworks, debates and challenges for feminist scholar-activism, including the works of scholar-activists such as Wendy Harcourt and Sunita Narain, and intersectional and transnational dilemmas.

Lesson 9: Feminist Movements and Democracy. Preliminary results of the FIERCE project

(Giada Bonu Rosenkranz – Scuola Superiore Normale)

In this lesson, Giada Bonu Rosenkranz, researcher from SNS, presents the FIERCE projects' preliminary results about the national and transnational conditions for the development of feminist movements in the 8 countries covered by the project over the period 2010-21. This includes an overview of the features of the new wave of feminist mobilization, the main issues, novelties in the organizational structure, the alliances, the outcomes and the repertoires of action.

Lesson 10: Global Challenges & Feminisms: Addressing/Challenging institutional politics & multilateral feminist advocacy beyond the EU

(Bertil Emrah Oder - Koç University, Magda Saginashvili – WIDE+)

In this lesson, two case studies are presented: in the first half, Bertil Emrah Oder, professor from Koç University (Turkey) explores the feminist strategies in her country, focusing on the reactions against the withdrawal of the Istanbul Convention and the role strategic litigation and coalition-building plays. In the other half, Magda Saginashvili describes feminist mobilization countering anti-gender narratives in Georgia.

3.2. Materials

The online repository of the course consists of a list of materials in each lesson, which includes different types of materials:

- Academic publications: including specific academic papers or other publications directly related to the lesson content. It is worth noting that other academic publications have been included if they are relevant to the national case study considered in the lesson. Thus, for instance, in lessons featuring interventions by activists from a specific country, academic publications recommended by partners from that country have been included. It is worth highlighting that among the academic publications included in the course, the two books published as part of the project have also been included:
 - [Smrdelj, Kuhar eds \(2025\): Anti-Gender Mobilizations in Europe and the Feminist Response, Productive Resistance \(2025\)](#)
 - [Bonu Rosenkranz, Della Porta eds \(2025\) Feminist Movements in Time and Space. A European Perspective \(2025\)](#)
- Materials from feminist movements: different materials shared by the feminist movements participating in the FIERCE course, including a variety of resources such as their social media pages, websites, publications, political manifestos, and other types of audiovisual materials produced as part of their activist activities.
- Project results: different outputs developed as part of project tasks.
 - [Fierce Dialogues: Podcast series](#)
 - [Public deliverables](#)

3.3. Final quiz

The final quiz to obtain the course certificate consists of 10 questions, detailed in the following table.

Lessons	Question	Right answer
1	<p>What does the critical frame analysis of the FIERCE project reveal?</p> <p>A. That anti-gender movements mainly focus on economic issues rather than cultural or identity concerns.</p> <p>B. That feminist movements increasingly adopt the framing strategies used by anti-gender actors to gain broader political support.</p> <p>C. That anti-gender actors use specific frames—such as “the best interest of children” or “natural law”—as political strategies to delegitimise gender equality and minority rights agendas.</p> <p>D. That the conservative Project 2025 uses frames defending gender equality as a political strategy to broaden its support.</p>	C
2	<p>According to the French and Turkish activists in the panel, what are the most effective strategies to counter the anti-gender backlash?</p> <p>A) Publishing academic research to inform public opinion without engaging in direct activism</p> <p>B) Quick reactivity with combined strategies such as street protests, digital activism, engaging with politicians, and building alliances with broader social movements and trade unions</p> <p>C) Prioritising internal debates within feminist groups to ensure ideological coherence before taking public action</p> <p>D) Relying on international institutions to pressure national governments through sanctions and declarations</p>	B
3	<p>Which of the following is not one of the eight main types of feminist and LGBTIQ+ response strategies to anti-gender mobilization identified in the FIERCE research?</p>	C

	<p>A) Strategic (non)-engagement B) Legal and institutional actions C) Enforcing gender-specific leadership quotas within organisations D) Digital activism</p>	
4	<p>How have the Women's Lobby of Slovenia organised for the Parallel Campaign for the European 2024 elections?</p> <p>Options: A) They organised a coalition, signed a memorandum with candidates and parties based on the European Women's Lobby manifesto, and held public discussions on gender equality. B) They primarily focused on lobbying for new gender equality legislation during the campaign. C) They organised protests and street actions D) They ran a media campaign to promote gender equality without engaging directly with political candidates.</p>	A
5	<p>What is "sophisticated racism" according to Victoria Showunmi's presentation?</p> <p>A. A form of racism based on systemic structures that disingenuously present themselves as anti-racist or equitable, often masked by politeness, inclusion rhetoric, or performative gestures. B. A strategic use of multicultural language and symbolic representation by institutions to maintain racial hierarchies without overt discrimination. C. A refined ideological belief that racial differences naturally determine intellectual and behavioural traits, expressed through academic or scientific discourse. D. An institutional framework that promotes meritocracy while quietly embedding selection criteria and norms that disproportionately exclude racialised individuals.</p>	A
6	<p>What is not a strategy highlighted by the three activists to address systemic inequalities faced by marginalised women?</p> <p>A. Legal action and litigation to defend rights B. Mutual aid and grassroots organising C. Institutional lobbying for policy change D. Individual self-advocacy without collective support</p>	D
7	<p>Which of the following statements best summarises the key lessons learned from the advocacy campaign described?</p> <p>A) Advocacy succeeds mainly through individual effort and emotional appeals. B) Including data is the best way to convince lawmakers. C) Successful advocacy depends on precise legal language, centring marginalized voices through inclusive and intersectional approaches, collective action, and combining data with authentic stories to influence lawmakers and the public. D) Advocacy is effective only if it focuses on the majority's needs and avoids complex legal language to simplify messages.</p>	C
8	<p>How does Birte Siim conceptualises "multiple crisis"?</p> <p>A. Multiple crises refer primarily to economic and political challenges that can be addressed separately for greater focus. B. Multiple crises encompass interconnected environmental, social, and economic issues that exacerbate one another, requiring feminist activism to respond in an integrated manner. C. Multiple crises are predominantly environmental concerns, largely independent of social and economic factors. D. Multiple crises denote distinct problems best approached sequentially rather than simultaneously by feminist movements.</p>	B

9	<p>What are the two main organisational structure trajectories observed in current European feminist movements according to FIERCE research?</p> <p>A) Increasingly centralised leadership with formal hierarchical structures B) Horizontal, grassroots organisational structures that prioritise radical claims and protests, alongside professionalised NGO-type structures that often engage with institutions C) Corporate-style organisations featuring paid staff and clearly defined roles D) Grassroots movements focusing primarily on online activism</p>	B
10	<p>10. Which of the following situations has been most determinant in shaping feminist movements' strategies and actions in Georgia since 2020?</p> <p>A) The consolidation of a pro-Western government that increased funding and support for feminist networks and civil society organisations focused on gender equality. B)The emergence of a strong coalition between feminist organisations and conservative political actors leading to compromises on gender equality policies. C) A series of progressive legal reforms passed by the government enhancing women's reproductive rights and protections against gender-based violence. D) The ruling party's withdrawal of support from feminist networks and civil society, alongside the redirection of state resources to far-right extremist groups opposing minority rights and promoting traditional family values.</p>	D

Table 1: Questions included in course's final quiz

4. List of course lecturers

Below are the biographies of the course presenters, including the texts they chose to share on the platform

Lise Rolandsen Augustin

I am an associate professor at Aalborg University (Denmark) where I am doing research on gender equality policies, transnational civil society and feminist movements in Europe. In the last few years, I have worked particularly on sexual harassment and policies and initiatives to create harassment-free organizations and environments. In addition, my focus has been on political intersectionality as well as inclusive policy-making processes from an intersectional perspective. I am also teaching at our master degree program in International Relations, particularly on the profile courses in Global Gender Studies.

Susi Meret

I am an Associate Professor at the Department of Politics and Society at the University of Aalborg, North Jutland in Denmark. My research interest is primarily with radical right-wing parties and movements in Europe, and specifically how these employ gender and gender-related issues in their discourses and mobilizations. I am an academic activist and particularly in the years 2015-19 I closely engaged with refugee-led mobilizations in Germany, also networking with activists in France, Italy and the Netherlands. I like and prefer to work with participatory methodologies and ethnography.

Deniz Bayram

I am a senior lawyer, campaigns and advocacy consultant, combining legal expertise with hands-on experience in women's rights, gender equality, climate justice, environment protection and energy policies. I specialize in advocacy, strategy building, and implementation in civil society. I have worked with organisations like Purple Roof Women's Shelter Foundation, Greenpeace, Change.org, and Human Rights Watch. I've contributed to various publications in gender justice and climate issues as (co-)author and editor. As part of my post-graduate education at Galatasaray University, I've completed my thesis on Corporate Environmental Crimes and Developments on International Criminal Law. I have been involved in strategic litigation, monitoring the case against Turkey's withdrawal from the Istanbul Convention since 2021 and the country's first climate lawsuit filed on behalf of young activists.

Maëlle Noir

Maëlle Noir is a member of #NousToutes' national steering committee, France's largest collective against gender-based violence (GBV). She is involved in press and public relations and research and is particularly interested in the fight against femicides. She co-supervises a study on the media coverage of femicides and coordinates the inter-orga féminicides, a coalition conducting the femicide census. She joined #NousToutes in 2020 through the GBV training program which offers online sessions with volunteers having trained more than 100,000 persons in less than a year. She co-organises the yearly protests for the 16 days of activism in November as well. She is also a researcher and part-time lecturer at the Irish Centre for Human Rights in feminist legal theory.

Jasna Podreka

Dr. Jasna Podreka is an Assistant Professor at the Faculty of Arts, University of Ljubljana. She specializes in the sociology of gender and social violence, focusing on intimate partner violence, femicide, and the impact of social structures on gender inequality. She completed her Ph.D. in Sociology at the University of Ljubljana, where she analyzed the social and institutional responses to femicide in Slovenia. Her work combines qualitative research with applied social science, aiming to improve awareness and institutional approaches to GBV. She also engages in public advocacy, contributing to media discussions and policy initiatives to prevent violence against women. Through her academic and public engagement,

she is committed to advancing gender equality and supporting violence prevention efforts in Slovenia and beyond.

Victoria Showunmi

Dr Victoria Showunmi is an Associate Professor at UCL's Institute of Education. Her interests are gender, identity, and race through intersectional lens, focusing on leadership and the lived experience of Black women and girls. She develops fresh frameworks on equity and social justice, showing how culture and cultural background could disrupt power structures and lead to transformative change. She is a member of the Gender and Education Executive, and is a chair for the British Educational Leadership Management and Administration Society, and of the International Studies SIG, American Educational Research Association, and co-convenor at the Gender Network, European Educational Research Association. She is on the editorial board of the Bloomsbury Series on Educational Leadership, and assistant editor for the International Journal of Leadership in Education.

Anikó Orsós

Anna Orsós is a women's rights officer at the European Roma Rights Centre (ERRC). She graduated in HR management and has worked in education since 1999. She was a regional coordinator at the National Educational Integration Network and at the Amrita association for integrated education of Roma youth. She has been promoting women's autonomy through non-formal learning and developed human rights activities with a gender perspective, including reports and expert recommendations on Roma women's rights. She ran a workshop at the Annual Global South Women's Forum on Sustainable Development on integrated/segregated and special education in Ruanda. Since 2021, she has been a member of the informal Roma Women's Network in Hungary.

Rafaela Pimentel

Domestic worker, activist, and feminist. Of Dominican origin, I have lived in Spain for 31 years, I have a son, and a first grandson who is giving me a lot of joy. I am founder of the collective Territorio Doméstico along with other fellow domestic and care workers and feminist companions. I also formed Senda de Cuidados (Part of care), an employment initiative for many migrant people who have difficulty entering the labor market. This project started in 2012. I have also written the prologue of the book Criada (Maid) of the publishing house Capitán Swing, which has been made a series on Netflix of 10 chapters.

Dominika Kasprowicz

Activist, feminist, journalist, educator, ESL teacher. Since 2016 involved in the the grassroots social movement Women's Strike. Since 2023, she has worked as an abortion doula, supporting Abortion Dream Team and Legalna Aborcja, a pro-abortion lobbying collective. She was a coordinator and organiser of protests in Ława and a member of the feminist association Brave. Member of the press team, and between 2020 and 2022, of the board of directors of the Polish Women's Strike Foundation. Hosted the feminist TV programme "This is War". Co-author of the Defend the Defenders campaign. Currently associated with the Legal Abortion and Abortion Dream Team collectives. Runs workshops on (empathetic) communication, misinformation prevention, journalism and social media for NGOs, and anti-discrimination. Studying needs-based coaching and NVC. Mother of 3 teenagers, yogi, vegan, minimalist, striving for zero waste. Singer-songwriter.

Birte Siim

Birte Siim is Professor Emerita in Gender Research, Department of Politics and Society, Aalborg University (AAU), Denmark. Her research interests include: Gender and Citizenship; Diversity and Intersectionality, Welfare States and Democracy, Populism and Nationalism;, Migration and Solidarity Activism. She is in the Advisory Board of FIERCE; edits the Palgrave Handbook on Gender and Citizenship

from Intersectional and Transnational Perspectives with P. Stoltz, 2023. Her publications cover topics such as gender representation in (Danish) political parties, EU citizenship and gender, migrant resistance and solidarity, intersectionality of migration, race, gender and sexuality, and the interplay of nationalism, activism and solidarity (movements).

Giada Bonu Rosenkranz

Giada Bonu Rosenkranz is a research fellow in project FIERCE at the Scuola Normale Superiore. After attending the Master's Program in Gender Studies and Politics at Roma Tre, she received her Ph.D. in Political Science and Sociology from the Scuola Normale Superiore, and is part of the Center for Research on Social Movements. Her research explores the links between feminist movements, democracy, and urban space, focusing on participatory methods. She is part of the editorial board of the journal on feminist studies DWF. Since 2021 she has also been part of the scientific council of the Gender Studies section of the Italian Sociology Association and directs, with Nicolò Bertuzzi and Jacopo Custodi, the series "Il cantiere delle idee" for Castelvechi Editore. She published the book: "Burn down the city. Gender, transfeminism and urban spaces". Florence: Unifir, with Federica Castelli and Serena Olcuire.

Bertil Emrah Oder

Bertil Emrah Oder is a professor of constitutional law and director of the Women and Gender Studies Center at Koç University, Istanbul. She holds the UNESCO Chair on Gender Equality under the UNITWIN Network. She has promoted human rights and gender equality in different research and capacity-building projects of the UN Women, Inter-Parliamentary, EU and Council of Europe on democratization, civic society, and constitutionalism. Her recent publications include: "Diversity and Plurality in Constitutional Context", Plurality and Diversity in Law: The Human Rights Paradigm, (with B. Gürcüoğlu), Laurence Burgorgue-Larsen (Ed.), International Academy of Comparative Law Series, Intersentia, 2023; "Feminist Struggle and the 1924 Constitution: In Search of Feminist Constitutionalism in the Early Republican Era", Diritto Pubblico Comparato ed Europeo, Special Issue, 2023/2."

Magda Saginashvili

Magda Saginashvili holds a Master's degree in European Policies from the University of Padova and a Master's in Gender Studies from Ivane Javakhishvili Tbilisi State University. She has been advocating for gender equality and social justice from a young age, initiating social learning and training courses to challenge gender stereotypes in Kakheti and Guria in 2017, Georgia. Magda has contributed to women's rights NGOs, served as a consultant for Georgia's Parliamentary Gender Equality Council, and currently holds a board position at Women in Development Europe (WIDE+). Additionally, she works as an invited research analyst at the NGO Femina and has pioneered a university course on gender-sensitive policymaking in Georgia. Her research interests include gender mainstreaming, women's political participation, GBV, and feminist movements.

Sonja Lokar

Sonja Lokar, professor of French language and sociology, graduated from Ljubljana University in 1971. She worked as a political analyst, MP in socialist and the first multiparty assembly of Slovenia. She had an active role in defending the freedom of birth in the Slovene Constitution of 1991, and in defending free-of-charge abortion and hormonal contraception - both rights are under sporadic attacks of political catholic right. She led a regional CEE Network for Gender Issues for 17 years, and a Stability Pact for SE Europe Gender Task Force for 10 years. In 2012 she was the president of the European Women's Lobby. She is now the president of the Women's Lobby of Slovenia.

Veronique Cerasoli

Véronique Cerasoli is a specialist in #feminism, #gender, and #LGBTI+ rights. As a trainer and consultant, she organizes and participates in numerous training sessions, workshops, symposiums, and conferences on these topics. She is an activist and board member of the association SOS Homophobie, where she is responsible for institutional advocacy and is the spokesperson for medically assisted procreation (MAP) and feminist issues. Véronique has gained extensive experience in inter-associative, international, and multidisciplinary projects related to her areas of expertise.

5. References

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